

Report on the Community Workshop for the RDMTraining4NFDI Proposal

Introduction

On July 2 2024, an online community workshop was conducted to discuss the proposal for "RDMTraining4NFDI," a project aimed at developing modular training concepts and materials for research data management (RDM). The workshop was hosted by Rabea Müller, Birte Lindstädt and Konrad Förstner. In the workshop, participants from various NFDI consortia had the opportunity to provide feedback, share their experiences, and collaborate on refining the proposal to better meet the diverse needs of their respective disciplines.

Participants

The workshop saw participation from multiple consortia, including NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Culture, GHGA, KonsortSWD, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Ing, Text+, NFDI4Microbiota, MaRDI, BERD@NFDI, DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRmat, NFDI4Earth, NFDI-MatWerk, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Memory, FAIRagro, NFDI4Energy, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, NFDIxCS, and NFDI4Immuno as well as participation from Base4NFDI. Specific individuals who consented to have their names published include:

- NFDI4Chem: Annett Schröter
- NFDI4Culture: Andrea Polywka
- GHGA: Julia Philipp, Julia Leimeister
- KonsortSWD: Anja Perry
- NFDI4Biodiversity: Daniel Tschink
- NFDI4Ing: Ute Trautwein-Bruns
- Text+: Thorsten Trippel, Andreas Witt
- MaRDI: Marco Reidelbach, Daniel Ramos
- DAPHNE4NFDI: Özgül Öztürk
- FAIRmat: Ahmed Mansour, Siamak Nakhaie
- NFDI4Earth: Carsten Keßler
- NFDI-MatWerk: Julia Mohrbacher, Flavio Soldera
- PUNCH4NFDI: Christiane Schneide, Baida Achkar
- NFDI4Memory: Marina Lemaire
- FAIRagro: Sophie Boße
- NFDI4Energy: Oliver Werth
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE: Thomas Zobel
- NFDIxCS: Jan Bernoth
- NFDI4Immuno: Sebastian Böhm
- Sophie Habinger: (no consortium, but eduTrain)

Workshop Agenda

The workshop was opened by outlining the agenda and the goals of the session. The importance of gathering participant feedback on the proposal was emphasized and the logistics of the workshop were discussed. The key points of the agenda included:

1. An overview of the proposal.
2. A discussion on the current status of RDM training within consortia in the main room.
3. Group discussions in breakout rooms to gather specific feedback and needs.
4. A detailed presentation of the proposal's timeline, structure, and expected outcomes.

Proposal Overview

The "RDMTraining4NFDI" proposal aims to create modular training resources for RDM that can be adapted for data-type-specific and discipline-specific training programs. The resources will be distributed as open educational resources (OERs) under a CC-BY license and will adhere to the FAIR principles.

Key components of the proposal include:

- Development of general and data-type-specific and domain-specific RDM training materials.
- Creation of a training program for data stewards and trainers.
- Development of certification standards for training programs.
- Distribution of materials through platforms such as Zenodo and DALIA.

The proposal is structured into three main tasks:

1. Overview and Compilation of Teaching Materials: Gathering and compiling existing RDM resources.
2. Development and Publication of OERs: Creating and publishing modular teaching materials.
3. Training Programs: Organizing summer schools, online workshops, and a certificate course for trainers and data stewards.

Timeline

The proposal timeline includes the following key milestones:

- Release Candidate 1: July 17 2024
- Feedback and Suggestions Period: July 17-22, 2024
- Processing Feedback and Release Candidate 2: July 22-24, 2024
- Copy Editing: July 24-30, 2024
- Final Submission: Aug 1, 2024
- Evaluation and Decision: October 11, 2024
- Initialization Phase Start: November 1, 2024

Discussions and Feedback

General Feedback

Participants provided valuable feedback, including the necessity for Letters of Commitment from pilot consortia and suggestions for broadening the proposal title to include Research Software Management. Concerns about the target audience were also addressed, emphasizing a focus on training data stewards and trainers to achieve a multiplier effect.

Status Quo Questions

In the main room, participants discussed and documented existing training programs, specific needs, and the importance of certification and accreditation. In the breakout rooms, each group shared their insights, which will help tailor the proposal to better suit the diverse requirements of different consortia and disciplines.

Question 1 - What do you have already? Which training material and training concepts exist in your consortium?

Each consortium shared their existing training materials and concepts:

- **NFDI4Chem** offers customized RDM training, hands-on workshops on ELNs, and a knowledge base.¹ They are developing a chemistry-specific exercise catalog for RDM workshops and developed a workshop concept on “FAIR Research Data Management: Basics for Chemists”.²
- **NFDI4Culture** has the Education Resource Finder (ERF)³ and plans to include their RDM basic courses.
- **DataPLANT** provides 1.5-day training courses, YouTube videos, slides, and articles available in their knowledge base.
- **GHGA** offers webinars, online courses on data protection, video recordings, and documentation on their services.
- **KonsortSWD** has an information and training platform for data curators⁴ and a nearly completed information platform based on the DCC Data Curation Lifecycle.⁵
- **NFDI4Biodiversity** supports various training programs, offering customised training, workshops, and a comprehensive set of OERs.
- **NFDI4Health** provides a training manual, standard training, and has initiated a Data Steward Pilot program.
- **NFDI4Ing** maintains a GitLab Educational Repository with training materials and an educational platform with self-learning resources.⁶
- **Text+** conducts regular presentations and workshops, contributing to conference programs and offering a help desk for RDM training.

¹ https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/de/

² Ann-Christin Andres, Benjamin Golub, Daniela Hausen, Sonja Herres-Pawlis, John Jolliffe, Johannes Liermann, Pascal Scherreiks, & Annett Schröter. (2023, August 16). FAIR Research Data Management: Basics for Chemists. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238499>

³ <https://nfdi4culture.de/resources/educational-resource-finder.html>

⁴ <https://rdm-compas.org/uber-rdm-compas>

⁵ <https://dcc.ac.uk/guidance/curation-lifecycle-model>

⁶ <https://education.nfdi4ing.de/startpage.html>

- **NFDI4Microbiota** has a training strategy document, a knowledge base, various workshops, as well as a Zenodo community where training materials from past events can be found.
- **BERD@NFDI** offers published materials on different aspects of RDM⁷ and an ongoing training program.⁸
- **DAPHNE4NFDI** provides lectures, seminars, workshops, and educational resources such as animated movies⁹ and Python courses.¹⁰
- **FAIRmat** conducts tutorials¹¹, on-site workshops, and creates educational materials on RDM and FAIR principles.¹²
- **NFDI4Earth** focuses on self-training¹³ and provides resources through the edutrain platform.¹⁴
- **NFDI-MatWerk** offers workshops, summer schools, and online lectures on various RDM topics.
- **PUNCH4NFDI** conducts community-specific training courses and tutorials, including multiple formats and topics.
- **NFDI4Memory** is developing a data literacy competence profile¹⁵, a training catalog, and a virtual RDM basic course.
- **NFDI4Objects** offers a collection of resources in a Commons Incubator¹⁶ and is currently developing a “Competency Framework” for competencies within the scope of N4O
- **FAIRagro** collaborates with agricultural universities and de.NBi to offer online and in-person training and a “How to Learn and Teach Research Data Management in Agrosystem Research - a FAIRagro Collection”.¹⁷
- **NFDI4Energy** collects teaching materials and makes them available in formats such as Markdown and LiaScript.¹⁸
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE** provides courses on image data analysis, talks, seminars, and a train-the-trainer workshop.
- **NFDI4CS** is working on material for FAIRification of Research Software, containerizing research data, and legal aspects of open-source software.
- **NFDI4Immuno** has just started and does not yet have any training material.
- **MaRDI** offers a course on RDM for mathematics¹⁹, publications²⁰, barcamps, and outreach activities such as "Pizza & Data", an afternoon in the maths department talking about RDM with having Pizza for everyone.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/berd-nfdi/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁸ <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/berd-academy/>

⁹ <https://youtu.be/lyhooPTv7w4>

¹⁰ <https://uni-siegen.sciebo.de/s/bccW5nyJ2BwR7yc>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/@TheNOMADLaboratory>

¹² https://zenodo.org/communities/fairmat_nfdi/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

¹³ <https://edutrain.nfdi4earth.de/>

¹⁴ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/academy>

¹⁵ <https://4memory.de/task-areas/task-area-4-data-literacy/>

¹⁶ <https://n4o.pages.gitlab.rlp.net/commons/en/incubatormain/>

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/11148701>

¹⁸

https://liascript.github.io/course/?https://raw.githubusercontent.com/NFDI4Energy/EFZN_rdm/main/README.md#19

¹⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/goergen/teaching?pli=1>

²⁰ <https://www.mardi4nfdi.de/resources/publications>

Question 2 - Which file formats do you use for your content (markdown, pdf, pptx , SCORM etc.) ? Which one would you like?

The NFDI consortia utilize a diverse range of file formats for their training materials. These formats cater to different needs, including presentation, documentation, interactive learning, and accessibility. Below is a summary of the preferred file formats used by each consortium and their preferences for future formats.

- **NFDI4Chem**: Courses are prepared with PowerPoint slides and shared as PDF files. Concepts are organized in Excel sheets.
- **NFDI4Culture**: Courses are prepared with PowerPoint (pptx) slides and shared as PDF files.
- **DataPLANT**: Utilizes Markdown, PDF, and PowerPoint (pptx) formats.
- **GHGA**: Prefers PDFs and videos (mp4).
- **KonsortSWD**: Reuses existing material in various formats.
- **NFDI4Biodiversity**: Uses Markdown, PDF, PowerPoint (pptx), mp4, and mp3.
- **NFDI4Cat**: No specific formats provided.
- **NFDI4Health**: Uses PDF and PowerPoint (pptx) files.
- **NFDI4Ing**: Prefers PowerPoint (ppt), PDF, and Markdown.
- **Text+**: Uses mostly PowerPoint (pptx), some PDF, and some Markdown files.
- **NFDI4Microbiota**: Utilizes PDF, Markdown, Google Docs and Slides and PowerPoint (pptx).
- **BERD@NFDI**: Uses PDF, live events, and self-learning modules.
- **DAPHNE4NFDI**: Prefers PDF and PowerPoint (pptx).
- **FAIRmat**: Utilizes Markdown, PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, Jupyter notebooks (ipynb), videos (mp4) and HTML.
- **NFDI4DataScience**: No specific formats provided.
- **NFDI4Earth**: Focuses on open formats such as Markdown and Jupyter notebooks.
- **NFDI-MatWerk**: Uses PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, Markdown and Jupyter notebooks
- **PUNCH4NFDI**: Utilizes PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, Markdown, HTML, and LaTeX for source files, with PDF and HTML for output.
- **NFDI4Objects**: Uses Markdown, RMarkdown (rmd), Quarto (qmd), PDF, DOCX, HTML and PowerPoint (ppt).
- **NFDI4Memory**: Prefers PowerPoint (pptx), HTML, and PDF.
- **FAIRagro**: Uses PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, DOCX, and Excel (xlsx).
- **NFDI4Energy**: Utilizes Markdown, implemented in LiaScript.
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE**: Uses PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, DOCX, and Markdown.
- **NFDIxCS**: Could use Markdown, PowerPoint (pptx), SCORM, but has no preferred format implemented.
- **NFDI4Immuno**: No training materials available yet.
- **MaRDI**: Uses LaTeX, PDF, HTML, and Markdown.
- **Kiel University**: Uses various formats, including LiaScript, Markdown, HTML, PDF, and SCORM.

The NFDI consortia employ a wide range of file formats for their training materials, with common formats including PowerPoint (pptx), PDF, and Markdown. Some consortia also utilize interactive formats such as Jupyter notebooks and LiaScript to enhance learning

experiences. This diversity in file formats reflects the varying needs and preferences of the consortia in delivering effective and accessible training materials.

Question 3 - How / where do you create and share your content?

The NFDI consortia employ various platforms and methods to create and share their training materials, ensuring accessibility and wide dissemination. Below is a summary of the preferred tools and platforms used by each consortium.

- **NFDI4Chem**: Utilizes Google Drive for content creation and Zenodo for sharing²¹, including a knowledge base.²²
- **NFDI4Culture**: Employs the Culture Information Portal²³ for content creation and shares via the Culture Knowledge Base²⁴ (Zenodo, TIB AV-Portal) and social media platforms like Mastodon and LinkedIn.
- **DataPLANT**: Uses GitHub for its knowledge base creation and shares content via YouTube.
- **GHGA**: Relies on internal platforms for content creation and shares via YouTube, their own website (ghga.de), and GitHub. They also use TeSS (Elixir) and social media (Mastodon, Bluesky, LinkedIn) for advertising and networking.
- **KonsortSWD**: Shares via rdm-compas.org.²⁵
- **NFDI4Biodiversity**: Shares via Zenodo, YouTube, Git (LiaScript, Jupyter Notebooks), Ilias, and their own Knowledge Base.
- **NFDI4Health**: Shares via Zenodo²⁶ and their homepage.²⁷
- **NFDI4Ing**: Uses GitLab / GitLab Pages and Zenodo for creation and sharing.
- **Text+**: Shares via Zenodo and their internal Nextcloud.
- **NFDI4Microbiota**: Shares via Zenodo and their Knowledge Base.
- **BERD@NFDI**: Creates content through various contributors and shares via the BERD Academy²⁸ and Zenodo.
- **DAPHNE4NFDI**: Uses Google Docs, Sciebo, and Moodle for creation and sharing.
- **FAIRmat**: Creates locally and uses GitHub for sharing, alongside their consortium website, YouTube, Zenodo, and presentations at conferences and workshops.
- **NFDI4Earth**: Shares via edutrain.nfdi4earth.de²⁹ and git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth.³⁰
- **NFDI-MatWerk**: Shares via their consortium website, Zenodo, and YouTube.
- **PUNCH4NFDI**: Uses their consortium GitLab platform and a public results page under an open license.
- **GAVO**: Utilizes GitHub, Codeberg, and a local SVN instance (transitioning to Git) for sharing.
- **NFDI4Objects**: Uses Nextcloud, Hedgedoc, Google Drive, Seafile for their working environment and shares via Zenodo, a future web portal, gitlab.rlp, newsletters, and social media (Mastodon, Instagram, LinkedIn).

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238498>

²² https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/de/

²³ <https://nfdi4culture.de/index.html>

²⁴ <https://nfdi4culture.de/resources/knowledge-base.html>

²⁵ <https://rdm-compas.org/uber-rdm-compas>

²⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/nfdi4health/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

²⁷ <https://www.nfdi4health.de/service/fair-training/nfdi4health-schulungsressourcen.html>

²⁸ <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/berd-academy/>

²⁹ <https://edutrain.nfdi4earth.de/>

³⁰ <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth>

- **NFDI4Memory**: Shares via virtual training courses (OES), Zenodo or other OER platforms, a MySQL-Database for their training catalog, and Google for presentations.
- **FAIRagro**: Creates and shares via PDF files, Google Drive, Zenodo, and their consortium website.
- **NFDI4Energy**: Uses GitHub and the Open Energy Academy for creation and sharing.
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE**: Shares via Zenodo, YouTube, GitHub, and their own knowledge base/website.
- **NFDIxCS**: Plans to use Zenodo for potential sharing of slides.
- **NFDI4Immuno**: Shares internally via Nextcloud.
- **MaRDI**: Uses Nextcloud (internal), Zenodo, and their consortium webpage for creation and sharing.
- **Kiel University**: Did not specify their methods.

Question 4 - Which license(s) do you use for your content?

The NFDI consortia employ a variety of licenses for their training materials, with a strong preference for open and permissive licenses that facilitate sharing and reuse. Below is a summary of the licenses used by each consortium.

- **NFDI4Chem**: CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4Culture**: CC BY
- **DataPLANT**: CC BY
- **KonsortSWD**: Mainly CC BY
- **NFDI4Biodiversity**: CC BY
- **NFDI4Health**: CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4Ing**: CC BY 4.0
- **Text+**: Default CC BY 4.0; others possible depending on third-party material
- **NFDI4Microbiota**: Mostly CC BY 4.0
- **BERD@NFDI**: Mostly CC BY 4.0
- **DAPHNE4NFDI**: MIT License
- **FAIRmat**: Predominantly CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4Earth**: Permissive open license (Creative Commons or similar)
- **NFDI-MatWerk**: Some use CC BY
- **PUNCH4NFDI**: GAVO: CC0; CC BY in agreement with material provider
- **NFDI4Objects**: CC BY 4.0, 3-clause BSD³¹
- **NFDI4Memory**: Recommended CC BY 4.0, creator's choice
- **FAIRagro**: OER Collection under CC0, slides and further resources likely CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4Energy**: CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE**: CC BY 4.0
- **NFDIxCS**: Default CC BY 4.0
- **NFDI4Immuno**: Not yet applicable
- **MaRDI**: Mostly CC BY 4.0

The NFDI consortia predominantly use the CC BY 4.0 license for their training materials, emphasizing the importance of open and permissive licensing to encourage sharing, reuse,

³¹ <https://opensource.org/license/bsd-3-clause>

and collaboration. Other licenses such as the MIT license, CC0, and 3-clause BSD are also used, depending on the specific requirements and preferences of the consortia.

Question 5 - What is missing? Which topics are not covered?

This question outlines the missing topics and gaps in the training materials identified by various NFDI consortia. These consortia provide essential training and resources to support RDM across different scientific domains. Despite their efforts, several key areas require further development to meet the needs of their communities. The following sections summarize the specific gaps reported by each consortium, highlighting common themes and unique needs.

- **NFDI4Chem:** Training for data stewards in chemistry, self-learning tutorials for ELN Chemotion +LabIMotion, Research Software Engineering, basics of Git/GitLab/GitHub.
- **NFDI4Culture:** Legal issues and hands-on approaches.
- **DataPLANT:** Legal aspects, basics of Git/GitLab/GitHub, in-depth RDM information.
- **GHGA:** Training on data access processes and services provided.
- **KonsortSWD:** RDM for new data types (e.g., social media), training in new software/programming languages.
- **NFDI4Biodiversity:** Courses on statistics and programming skills (e.g., Git basics, Python, statistical models).
- **NFDI4Health:** Concept and implementation of a (Spring/Summer) School for researchers/Data stewards.
- **NFDI4Ing:** Specific content on tools, different types of data, or processes.
- **Text+:** Modular set of RDM essentials, slides/materials in editable formats.
- **BERD@NFDI:** Keeping track of new developing topics.
- **DAPHNE4NFDI:** Standardization and inventory of training materials, need for more trainers.
- **FAIRmat:** Professional legal support, RDM Game Kits, illustration resources.
- **NFDI4Earth:** Provision of an NFDI Learning Management System for deploying self-training materials.
- **NFDI-MatWerk:** More trainers, practical examples related to MatWerk, open Python courses, ELN instances for training.
- **PUNCH4NFDI:** Findable and searchable training material, basic RDM introduction, overview of available training and courses.
- **NFDI4Objects:** Basic data literacy training, contact with regional RDM programmes, competency framework for RDM in disciplines.
- **NFDI4Memory:** Skills profile development, digital source criticism, FAIR principles for qualitative methods.
- **FAIRagro:** Learning resources focused on agricultural sciences, digital field books.
- **NFDI4Energy:** Legal aspects in RDM, "how-tos" for appropriate RDM, research software engineering content.
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE:** Not specified.
- **NFDI4CS:** Not yet started.
- **NFDI4Immuno:** Not yet started.

The NFDI consortia have identified a range of topics that are currently missing from their training materials. These include both general and domain-specific needs such as legal aspects, programming skills, data literacy, and practical examples. Addressing these gaps will enhance the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of the training programs offered by the NFDI consortia.

Question 6 - Are your training and content creation activities internationally connected? If so how? (e.g. ELIXIR)

This question summarizes the international connections of training and content creation activities across various NFDI consortia. These connections are crucial for fostering global collaboration and ensuring that training materials meet international standards and reach a wider audience.

- **NFDI4Chem:** No formal international connections, but training is offered in English and has attracted participants from outside Germany.
- **NFDI4Culture:** No English courses presented yet, but English RDM training offers are recommended.³²
- **DataPLANT:** No known international connections.
- **GHGA:** Collaborates with ELIXIR (German node, de.NBI) to increase visibility and connect user communities. Collaborative courses and webinars are under discussion. Involved in international data protection efforts.
- **KonsortSWD:** No current international connections, but plans for outreach activities and translation of materials to English are underway.
- **NFDI4Biodiversity:** Focuses primarily on the national level, but has connections to international projects such as ELIXIR, SORTÉE, and EOSC.
- **NFDI4Health:** No known international connections, but cooperation with Health-RI (Netherlands) is planned.
- **NFDI4Ing:** No known international connections.
- **Text+:** Collaborates with international organizations such as CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, nestor, and CTS.
- **NFDI4Microbiota:** Connected to The Carpentries, RDM training in English that has attracted participants from abroad, collaboration with de.NBI for training.
- **BERD@NFDI:** No known international connections.
- **DAPHNE4NFDI:** Cooperates with LEAPS, ESUO, ENSA, LENS, PaNOSC, EOSC, ExpanDS, ORSO, and ISPyB Consortium. Engages in workshops and outreach activities.
- **NFDI-MatWerk:** Offers training in international study programs, inviting masters students from other European countries.
- **PUNCH4NFDI:** Not actively connected internationally, but aware of initiatives such as the HEP Software Foundation³³ and GAVO, a data center involved in the development of interoperability standards in astronomy at the IVOA.³⁴
- **GAVO data center** is involved in international astronomy standards and European projects such as ESCAPE.

³² <https://nfdi4culture.de/resources/educational-resource-finder.html>

³³ <https://hepsoftwarefoundation.org/workinggroups/training.html>

³⁴ <https://ivoa.net/>

- **NFDI4Objects**: Not connected internationally, but uses the FAIR4S-OER Framework of EOSC for competency framework development.
- **NFDI4Memory**: Not actively connected internationally but aware of initiatives and tries to connect with universities in the USA and German-speaking countries. Looks to the EOSC Pillar for training material.
- **FAIRAgro**: Collaborates with de.NBI for training, collects materials from international organizations like CGIAR and Ag Data Commons, and exchanges with Swedish Agricultural University (SLU).
- **NFDI4Energy**: No known international connections.
- **NFDI4BIOIMAGE**: Connected to de.NBI, ELIXIR, Galaxy, German BioImage, and EuroBioImage.
- **NFDIxCS**: No international connections yet, but preparations are underway.
- **NFDI4Immuno**: To be discussed.

While some NFDI consortia have established international connections and collaborations, others primarily focus on national activities or are in the early stages of exploring international partnerships. Strengthening these connections can enhance the quality and reach of training materials, promote best practices globally, and facilitate knowledge exchange across borders.

Topic 04 - Group Discussion Summary

In the breakout sessions, small groups discussed key training needs, identified what is missing, explored how RDMTraining4NFDI can support the creation of content and training in their consortia, gathered feedback on the proposed service and training formats, and offered further suggestions for improvement.

Group 1 Discussion Outcomes

Participants from NFDI4Chem raised concerns about the cost-benefit ratio of current training initiatives, e.g. dini Nestor AG UAG Schulungen Train the Trainer.³⁵ They suggest that accreditation might not be useful due to the specific needs of their target group. They proposed a 2-3 day event for exchanging experiences on training creation and delivery at universities with other NFDI consortia. NFDI4Culture raised the question of cooperation with FDM Landesinitiativen to align generic content, highlighting the importance of didactic and instructional design knowledge. BERD emphasized the need for understanding specific requirements, while NFDI4Objects advocated for consolidating best practices centrally, focusing on organization and clarification rather than creating new materials.

DAPHNE supported the need for organizational and structuring support along with instructional design. DataPLANT emphasized the necessity of content modules for legal aspects and standardized entry-level training for data stewards, including basic GitHub and GitLab knowledge. MatWerk suggested that a summer school could serve as a good community multiplier. NFDI4Memory proposed discussing quality criteria for accreditation and sustainability of training post-financing. NFDIxCS highlighted the need for software management training, including coding best practices.

³⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/10122153>

The group agreed on the necessity of organizational support, instructional design, and centralized didactics expertise.

Group 2 Discussion Outcomes

GHGA mentioned that while there is no need for additional RDM training due to ELIXIR, there is a need for people power and outreach to researchers. ZB MED proposed creating a trainer network to support each other and exchange knowledge on specific topics, including legal questions, which was supported by PUNCH4NFDI. NFDI4Objects highlighted the challenge of general RDM training due to the diversity of disciplines, suggesting the trainer network focus on specific topics. NFDI4Energy highlighted the need for guidance on legal issues and teaching material on FAIR research software. NFDI4Biodiversity noted the need for basic tool training in Git and statistics, and interdisciplinary tool training for handling different data types. MaRDI highlighted a general lack of understanding of RDM among mathematicians, suggesting cultural change and general practice discussions.

The group emphasized the usefulness of a trainer network and the need for training in tools and handling different data types, as well as support for professional legal advice and resources for creating high-quality illustrations for training materials.

Group 3 Discussion Outcomes

In its early stage, NFDI4Immuno welcomed all input. General needs identified included didactical concepts, a central repository for materials, and an understanding of key RDM topics such as Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), repositories, quality assurance, licenses, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), privacy issues, certification, FAIR, CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, and Identity and Access Management (IAM). NFDI-MatWerk emphasized the need for didactical concepts and ensuring that content does not become outdated.

Feedback on the proposed service indicated concerns about the time-consuming nature of training activities and the need for accreditation and modularity in training content. Suggestions for improvement included refresher courses for trainers, blended learning approaches, and addressing the limited time available for training.

Workshop Conclusion

Throughout the workshop, participants engaged in lively discussions about the specific needs and challenges faced by NFDI consortia in research data management (RDM) training. The overarching goal of "RDMTraining4NFDI" to develop modular training concepts and materials resonated strongly with the diverse group of stakeholders present. These materials are intended to support the creation of high-quality, standardized RDM training programs across all consortia within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

Key outcomes from the discussions highlighted the necessity for:

1. **Centralized Support and Expertise:** Participants emphasized the need for centralized support in instructional design, didactics, and organizational structuring.

This support is crucial for adapting generic training materials into discipline-specific contexts effectively.

2. **Certificate Development:** The proposal aims to integrate standards for certification, which will be a primary focus for NFDI consortia, and this will be emphasized as an additional work package.
3. **Trainer Network and Collaboration:** There was widespread agreement on the value of establishing a trainer network to facilitate knowledge exchange and support among peers. This network can play a vital role in addressing specific topics such as legal aspects, software management, and handling diverse data types. Consortia expressed the desire for "RDMTraining4NFDI" to provide didactic offerings based on models such as The Carpentries and to foster the development of a robust trainer community.
4. **Modularity and Adaptability:** The modular approach of "RDMTraining4NFDI" was welcomed as it allows for flexibility and adaptation to meet the diverse needs of different disciplines within the consortia. The emphasis on OERs under a CC-BY license ensures accessibility and promotes the FAIR principles.
5. **Long-Term Sustainability:** Participants underscored the importance of sustainability beyond initial funding cycles. This includes ongoing support for updating and refining training materials, as well as mechanisms for accreditation and quality assurance.

Moving forward, the workshop outcomes will inform the further development and implementation of "RDMTraining4NFDI". Participants are encouraged to provide further feedback on the RDMTraining4NFDI proposal through registration for the first release candidate: [Community Feedback Form](#).